

COMPLIANCE RISK – WHAT IS KNOWN ABOUT IT IN GEORGIA?**Kodelashvili Lia***PHD Candidate, East European University, Tbilisi, Georgia***Abstract**

As global attention to non-financial risks grows, compliance risk management has become a key component of sound governance in the banking sector. While this field has evolved internationally since the early 2000s, regulatory approaches and academic analysis remain underdeveloped in Georgia. This study examines the national regulatory framework governing compliance risk management in the Georgian banking sector, alongside the country's international obligations. Employing qualitative document analysis and comparative methods, the research identifies significant gaps, including weak enforcement mechanisms, the absence of a standardized definition of compliance risk, and a lack of clearly defined management practices. The findings highlight the need for a unified regulatory approach aligned with international standards to ensure effective compliance risk governance.

Keywords: Compliance, Compliance Risk, Compliance Risk Management, Corporate Governance, Compliance Function, Regulatory Framework.

Introduction

In recent years, increasing attention has been directed toward non-financial risk management, with particular emphasis on compliance risk. Recognized as a distinct category, compliance risk management has gained significant prominence since the early 21st century.

As a fundamental component of corporate governance, it ensures that organizations operate within legal and ethical boundaries, thereby fostering trust and supporting long-term sustainability [1]. Compliance risk is inherent to all business entities due to the necessity of adhering to legal requirements, regulations, and standards across the jurisdictions in which they operate or serve clients. To maintain competitiveness, companies often seek to streamline service delivery and maximize profitability, which may create compliance dilemmas. Nonetheless, organizations are expected to uphold transparency, accountability, and high ethical standards while fully complying with legal obligations.

To guide institutions, international bodies such as ISO, the Basel Committee on Banking Supervision (BCBS), the European Banking Authority (EBA), and the OECD have developed widely recognized principles and standards for compliance risk management. EU member states are mandated to harmonize national legislation with European directives and relevant international standards. Following the Association Agreement, Georgia committed to aligning its domestic legal framework with European norms, including Basel Committee guidelines [2].

Despite the growing global focus on compliance risk, there remains a notable lack of research on its management in Georgia. This study, therefore, examines whether the national regulatory framework adequately supports effective compliance risk management following international standards and Georgia's obligations. The objective is to enhance understanding, identify regulatory gaps, and contribute to the advancement of compliance practices in the sector.

This research employs a qualitative methodology, involving systematic analysis of Georgian banking regulations alongside comparative evaluation of international standards and academic literature.

1. Literature Review

The banking sector is particularly susceptible to compliance risks due to its responsibility for managing client funds and providing services involving third-party assets. These functions heighten the sector's exposure, as banks must ensure transparency, accountability, and adherence to legal standards to maintain stakeholder trust and ethical operations.

Effective compliance risk management is crucial for achieving strategic stability [3]. It functions as both a risk mitigation tool and a framework for responsible risk-taking within legal boundaries, supporting sustainable organizational objectives [4]. However, the primary purpose of compliance risk management is not limited to risk reduction. Rather, it supports informed and strategic risk-taking within the boundaries of applicable laws and regulations, enabling organizations to pursue their goals responsibly and sustainably.

To better understand the topic, it is important to define compliance risk. While definitions vary slightly, they consistently describe it as the risk of legal or regulatory sanctions, financial loss, or reputational damage resulting from non-compliance with laws, regulations, codes of conduct, or self-regulatory standards [5, 6, 7].

Academic literature often uses terms like compliance, compliance management, and compliance risk management interchangeably. However, important distinctions exist. Compliance management represents a more comprehensive approach, encompassing establishing and maintaining compliance standards [8]. It broadly refers to an organization's overall adherence to legal and internal obligations [9], while compliance risk management is a more focused subset that deals specifically with identifying and managing the risks associated with non-compliance [10]. It is a targeted approach within risk management that specifically focuses on the risks arising from non-compliance. Its purpose is to identify, assess, and manage these risks to

ensure compliance with legal and regulatory requirements, while protecting the organization's integrity and reputation [6].

A sound compliance management system, such as that outlined in ISO 37301, helps organizations demonstrate their commitment to legal and ethical conduct [11]. It also reinforces accountability, strengthens governance, and builds stakeholder confidence [12], allowing organizations to navigate today's complex regulatory environments responsibly [13].

2. Methodology and Research Procedure

This study employs a qualitative research approach to explore the regulatory framework for compliance risk management in Georgia's banking sector. The central research question guiding this study is: Does the national regulatory framework in Georgia adequately ensure effective compliance risk management in line with international standards and obligations? Qualitative methods are suitable for interpreting the context and meaning of legal norms and institutional practices rather than quantifying data. The primary method is document analysis of national normative acts and international best practices, supported by systematic and comparative analysis.

Research Procedure: The study began with a review of documents from the Legislative Herald of Georgia (www.matsne.gov.ge) and the National Bank of Georgia's website (www.nbg.gov.ge), supplemented by literature from ISO, the Basel Committee, ScienceDirect, Google, and Google Scholar. Search keywords included: Compliance, Compliance Risk Management, Corporate Governance, and Compliance Function. To trace the origins and evolution of compliance risk regulation in Georgia, no time restriction was set for the search. Relevant normative acts were identified using keyword searches across document titles, full texts, and the advanced search function on www.matsne.gov.ge. All retrieved materials were reviewed and analyzed based on their relevance to the study's objectives.

3. Regulatory Development of Compliance Risk in Georgia

3.1. Compliance Risk. The concept of "compliance risk" was first formally introduced in Georgia in 2008 through the National Bank of Georgia's (NBG) Regulation on Risk Management in Commercial Banks. Defined as "the risk of legal and regulatory sanctions, financial losses, or reputational damage resulting from non-compliance," the regulation (Article 44) required banks to incorporate compliance risk into their internal control systems [14]. According to Article 5, Subparagraph 2(f) of the same Regulation, commercial banks were required to establish a risk management policy that, among other aspects, included the development of an internal control system to ensure compliance with both internal regulatory documents (such as policies, procedures, and rules) and applicable legislative requirements, that is, to address compliance risk. Chapter 10 of the Regulation elaborated on compliance risk management expectations. Banks were mandated to identify and assess risk factors, such as the

complexity of their operations, non-compliance incidents, and legal claims, that could adversely affect their financial stability. They were also expected to manage these risks through dedicated policies, procedures, skilled staff, and robust controls.

Following the 2008 global financial crisis, the Basel Committee enhanced its regulatory guidance, replacing Basel II with the more risk-sensitive Basel III framework [15]. In line with these developments, Georgia revised its banking regulations: Order No. 71 was repealed and replaced by Order No. 18/04 in 2014. The new regulation explicitly required banks to establish dedicated compliance units (Article 42), formalizing expectations that had been implied in the 2008 framework. Notably, a similar requirement had already been implied in the earlier 2008 regulation, which called for the establishment of an internal control system to ensure compliance with internal policies, procedures, and legislative requirements, i.e., to manage compliance risk. Therefore, although the 2008 regulation did not explicitly mandate the creation of a compliance unit, the underlying expectations were consistent.

The 2014 Regulation also clarified the roles of the Supervisory Board, Directorate, and control units - Internal Audit, Compliance, and Risk Management - emphasizing their independence and coordination. It categorized nine key risks, including compliance risk, and outlined both bank and NBG supervisory responsibilities. Furthermore, the regulation stipulates that the organizational structure must guarantee the independence of control units from those departments directly involved in operational activities. In addition to defining the responsibilities of commercial banks, the Regulation also specifies the obligations of the NBG in its supervisory role, particularly concerning the enforcement of the Regulation's requirements. To enforce these requirements, the NBG was expected to assess commercial banks through the CAMEL framework and thematic inspections, evaluating the adequacy of compliance risk management systems and ensuring risks were properly identified, assessed, and mitigated.

The next stage of regulatory changes for the banking sector, as well as for Georgia as a whole, began following the signing of the Association Agreement

3.2. The Association Agreement. On June 2, 2014, Georgia signed the Association Agreement (AA) with the European Union, including the Deep and Comprehensive Free Trade Area (DCFTA), committing to gradually align its national legislation with EU standards. The AA/DCFTA, which entered into full force in July 2016, encompasses numerous sectors, including the financial sector (Article 122).

Under the Agreement, Georgia is obligated to adopt internationally recognized standards for regulating and supervising financial services, including the Basel Core Principles for Effective Banking Supervision (BCP), and to implement measures to combat tax evasion and avoidance. These commitments are outlined in Article 323 and Annex XV-A, which lists the specific EU legislative acts and international instruments to be adopted within designated timeframes.

The Basel Core Principles provide a comprehensive framework for sound banking supervision, governance, and risk management. They serve as global benchmarks, regardless of a country's supervisory model. The IMF and World Bank assess compliance with the BCP through the Financial Sector Assessment Program (FSAP), ensuring consistency with international best practices [16].

Before 2014, Georgia's adoption of international standards, including those set by the Basel Committee, was voluntary. However, the AA/DCFTA formalized the requirement for legislative alignment and integration of these standards into national regulation, marking a new phase in the development of Georgia's financial regulatory framework.

3.3. Information Disclosure. The Basel regulatory framework is based on 3 pillars: Pillar I - Minimum Capital Requirements, Pillar II - Supervisory Review, and Pillar III - Market Discipline. Introduced under Basel II and retained in Basel III, these pillars promote sound risk management and transparency within the banking sector. Together, they strengthen financial stability.

In Georgia, Pillar III was implemented through NBG Order No. 92/04 (June 22, 2017), which established the "Procedure for Disclosure of Information by Commercial Banks under Pillar 3." Market discipline is crucial for all stakeholders; however, the core operations of commercial banks are typically highly confidential. Consequently, comprehensive information on how banks manage third-party assets (such as deposits and loans) and the standards they employ to safeguard these assets is not readily accessible. To provide stakeholders with meaningful insight into the banks in which they have an interest, the Basel Committee, followed by local banking supervisors, has established a unified regulatory framework governing the disclosure of such information.

Under this regulation, commercial banks are required to publish both quantitative and qualitative information related to capital adequacy, corporate governance, and risk management. Article 6 specifically obligates banks to disclose details on their internal control and risk management systems, including the roles and relationships of key structural units: the Supervisory Board, Executive Body, Risk Management, Compliance Unit, and Internal Audit [17]. Section 3(c) outlines the required components of these disclosures, such as control mechanisms by risk type, delegated authority, responsibilities, and the overall risk management framework. This includes the bank's approach to compliance risk - continuing obligations first introduced in 2008 (Article 44) [14].

By 2017, commercial banks were expected to have developed a mature compliance function, including clearly defined interactions between the Compliance Unit and other risk-related units. The regulation also introduced disclosure requirements related to remuneration policies. In particular, banks must ensure that compensation for personnel in risk and compliance functions is not directly tied to business income, thus safeguarding the independence of these control units.

In summary, the 2017 regulation formalized the obligation for commercial banks to disclose their compliance risk management practices and the Compliance Unit's role within the broader risk framework. While compliance responsibilities date back to 2008, the explicit requirement to establish a dedicated Compliance Unit appeared in 2014, followed by disclosure obligations in 2017.

The next section will discuss another regulatory development linked to the Association Agreement: the Corporate Governance Code for Commercial Banks and its implications for compliance risk management.

3.4. Corporate Governance. Corporate governance became a formal legislative requirement in Georgia's banking sector relatively late, only in September 2018, under the country's obligations under the Association Agreement (AA/DCFTA). The Corporate Governance Code for Commercial Banks, approved by the NBG, entered into force on September 26, 2018, and applies to all commercial banks in Georgia. The Code governs the roles and responsibilities of the Supervisory Board, risk management frameworks, and internal controls [18]. Between 2018 and 2024, the NBG amended the Code nine times. Under its most recent version, where specific corporate governance matters are not explicitly regulated, banks, branches of foreign banks, and subsidiaries are required to follow best practices recognized in the field, subject to NBG approval. These best practices include standards issued by the Basel Committee, Directive 2013/36/EU of the European Parliament and Council, OECD guidelines, and principles of the London Stock Exchange, among others (Article 1) [19].

With the adoption of the Code, the NBG repealed its prior Regulation on Risk Management in Commercial Banks [20], which had previously defined compliance risk and detailed the responsibilities of the compliance unit. These included setting risk tolerance limits, aligning policies with the bank's strategy, assigning responsibilities across organizational levels, applying zero-tolerance policies to specific violations, and conducting regular compliance reviews (Article 41).

3.4.1. Compliance Unit. A significant development relevant to this study concerns the Compliance Unit. Under the Corporate Governance Code, the Compliance Unit is one of three designated control functions, alongside Risk Management and Internal Audit (Article 2, paragraph 1(i)). These functions are responsible for evaluating the effectiveness and efficiency of internal processes, providing objective assessments, and reporting to the appropriate governing bodies. An amendment introduced by NBG Order №17/04 on February 9, 2021, expanded the responsibilities of the Supervisory Board, mandating that it ensure the Compliance Unit's independence, grant it sufficient authority, and provide it with unrestricted access to the board (Article 4, paragraph 1(o)).

The Compliance Unit is formally recognized as a structural division responsible for implementing the compliance function. Its core responsibilities include:

1) Ensuring the bank's compliance with legislative requirements, internal policies, and procedures; 2) Identifying and assessing actual and potential compliance risks; 3) Advising the Supervisory Board and Management Board on compliance risk management and control strategies; 4) Raising staff awareness on compliance-related issues.

Previously, under the now-repealed Regulation on Risk Management in Commercial Banks (20), the Compliance Unit was also tasked with human resource-related responsibilities, such as: Evaluating compensation programs from a compliance perspective; Identifying key personnel and setting rotation limits; Assessing the adequacy of training programs; Evaluating the competence of governing bodies; Defining the bank's risk tolerance in its business activities.

Currently, the Corporate Governance Code remains the only active regulatory instrument explicitly defining the framework for compliance risk management in Georgian commercial banks.

3.4.2. Compliance Risk – Identification and Evaluation. The Corporate Governance Code retains the Compliance Unit's responsibility to identify and evaluate material and potential compliance risks - a function previously detailed in the now-repealed Regulation on Risk Management in Commercial Banks. However, the current legal framework no longer defines compliance risk or outlines assessment procedures. In such cases, banks must refer to Article 1(2) of the Code, which permits the adoption of internationally recognized standards, such as the Basel Committee's 2005 guidance on compliance, subject to NBG approval. This means that banks themselves must propose best practices for endorsement before implementation. While the Code stresses risk identification and evaluation, it lacks the procedural specificity that the repealed regulation once provided.

According to ISO 31000:2018, risk assessment entails identifying, analyzing, and evaluating risks to manage uncertainty and potential impact [21, 22]. Both qualitative and quantitative methods are recognized in the literature as viable approaches to compliance risk assessment. However, the NBG has not adopted a unified methodology. Absence of standardized procedures, enforcement mechanisms may be inconsistently applied or ineffective. The World Bank underscores this issue, emphasizing that enforcement, not merely the existence of sanctions, is critical for the effective implementation of corporate governance [18].

Without effective enforcement, the requirements set out in the Code may not be fully implemented, and the quality of corporate governance in practice may remain inadequate. According to the World Bank (2021), consistent enforcement is identified as a key factor in the successful adoption of corporate governance best practices, particularly in countries with developing markets. This includes: (1) enforcement of mandatory regulations, and (2) strict supervisory oversight of the implementation of corporate governance codes [18].

The Basel Committee's Principle 26 requires supervisors, such as Georgia's NBG, to ensure that banks maintain a permanent, independent, and

adequately staffed compliance function, with board-level oversight [16]. Fulfilling Association Agreement obligations requires more than referencing compliance in the Code; it demands a dedicated regulatory framework on compliance risk management. Moreover, the NBG must be capable of evaluating the independence and effectiveness of compliance functions. For example, the U.S. Federal Reserve emphasizes tailoring compliance programs to each institution's risk profile [7]. Similarly, the Basel Committee notes (note 34) that limiting compliance functions to AML alone contradicts its broader expectations. The compliance function must encompass a broader scope, as emphasized both in the Corporate Governance Code and the Basel Committee's guidance [23]. Internationally, this broader view is operationalized through concrete guidance. In a 2021 address at the BFSI Summit, the Deputy Governor of the Reserve Bank of India highlighted the Bank's most recent compliance guidance, which assigns direct responsibility for compliance culture and risk management to the board of directors [24]. The guidance advises banks to adopt a formal compliance policy, define clear appointment procedures for the Chief Compliance Officer (CCO), and establish fixed terms and board-approved mandates for the CCO. This illustrates how regulators not only recognize compliance as integral to corporate governance but also operationalize it through concrete regulatory instruments.

In contrast, Georgia's current regulatory framework remains underdeveloped. A review of the NBG website reveals no detailed, updated regulations on compliance risk management. Relevant guidance is limited to the repealed 2008 and 2014 "Risk Management in Commercial Banks" regulations and the Corporate Governance Code, which only partially and incompletely incorporates Basel Committee standards.

Conclusion

An analysis of the 2008 and 2014 regulations issued by the National Bank of Georgia (NBG) shows that compliance risk management has been a legislative requirement for commercial banks since 2008. From 2014, banks were obligated to establish dedicated compliance units within their internal control systems, conduct quarterly compliance risk assessments, and report findings to the NBG. Oversight of these obligations was intended through CAMEL ratings or thematic inspections.

The 2014 Association Agreement marked a pivotal moment, committing Georgia to align its regulatory framework with EU directives and Basel Committee standards. Although the NBG has actively developed relevant regulations, enforcement and implementation remain inadequate.

The current framework is deficient in two key areas: (1) it lacks effective mechanisms for the NBG to assess banks' compliance risk profiles, risk appetite, and management quality, indicating weak enforcement; and (2) it fails to clearly define the compliance function's role, status, independence, and safeguards—par-

ticularly regarding the Chief Compliance Officer's authority, qualifications, budget, and accountability [16, 6].

Notably, the repealed Regulation on Risk Management in Commercial Banks provided a more detailed framework for compliance units than the current Corporate Governance Code, whose provisions are now only partially reflected in existing norms.

The World Bank emphasizes that regulatory frameworks alone are insufficient without effective enforcement. Sanctions, whether financial or non-financial, only ensure compliance if actively applied. Before enforcement, a standardized regulatory approach must be established to serve as a clear benchmark, enabling mechanisms that ensure sustained compliance.

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